

D3.6 Website and project logo

WP3: Raising visibility and impacts

T3.2: The Platform and the Multi-channel communication

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Technical references

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* PU = Public

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1. Introduction

1.1. Aims of the document

The aim of this document is to describe the visual identity and landing page development process of the EIC Communities project.

The following chapters describe and anticipate some key sections of the website, that will be officially online in March 2024; the website sections and features were discussed and validated with the EIC Programme Managers (PM) during the co-creation workshop held in Brussels in October 2023.

1.2. Responsibility of the consortium

WP3 leader ICONS is accountable for the design, delivery, management and monitoring of the website.

ICONS oversaw the identification of the most effective visual identity for the project and the landing page. In the upcoming months, ICONS will develop the website, from content drafting to graphic elements.

1.3. The legacy of FETFX, EIC Communities and DEEPSYNC

For many years, FETFX, a FET-funded project, has been at the forefront of driving innovative research initiatives across a wide range of scientific fields. As one of the pioneering projects to bring together science, industry, and society through the storytelling communication strategy, FETFX has collaborated to create a community of both experts and non-experts around the deep tech sector. Building upon this valuable legacy, the new project EIC Communities fosters vibrant communities centred around EIC-funded projects.

The consortium has decided to brand the EIC Communities platform with the name "**DEEPSYNC**" for both strategic and sustainability reasons.

Firstly, DEEPSYNC is highly a descriptive and evocative name, immediately conveying the platform's primary objective of fostering deep synergies among various communities, including entrepreneurs, researchers, policy makers, tech scouts, investors, and more.

To achieve this goal, the platform seeks to distance itself from its official name, "EIC Communities", in favour of a name that resonates better with its diverse stakeholder base: the goal is to make the platform accessible to a broad audience, including those who are not experts in the EIC field. The choice of clear and easily understandable words will contribute to this objective. The project website will duly highlight that DEEPSYNC is "powered by the EIC Communities project".

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Finally, the choice of the name 'DEEPSYNC' is closely tied to the platform's sustainability plans. If all planned measures are successfully implemented, such as the effective management of Communities of Practice (CoPs), the platform's usefulness to both EIC Communities and external stakeholders, and partner commitment to its maintenance beyond the project's conclusion, the platform could potentially continue to exist under this name, serving as an enduring entry point for the EIC community of innovators.

In line with the abovementioned points, and for a consistent communication strategy, the project decided to adopt the unique hashtag "#Deepsync_eu" thus simplifying social media promotion and branding efforts and making it easier for the platform to engage with its audience effectively. For instance, using the name "EIC Communities" for social media when promoting the platform would make it difficult to track hashtags.

2. Visual identity

The EIC Communities project, and so its brand identity, is the natural continuation of the FETFX project. The visual identity is devised to promote the idea of vibrant communities able to collaborate towards a common goal, reinterpreting and readapting a concept already present in the first project. The graphic elements want to inspire dynamism and drive for innovation.

The project focuses on individuals and aims to assist EIC beneficiaries. Consequently, the visual identity will feature imagery representing innovators, investors, policymakers, and citizens—everyone who can be involved in and affected by the project. The ICONS team is actively working towards fair and inclusive portrayals of individuals, regardless of gender identity. This initiative is committed to dispelling stereotypes and championing truthful, diverse representations. With a strong dedication to celebrating people of all ages and backgrounds, it envisions a society that values authenticity and embraces diversity as a catalyst for progress. In our pursuit of this vision, we'll also employ AI when appropriate, ensuring in its application transparency and clarity. Furthermore, the design will also prioritize inclusivity with respect to considerations related to accessibility and disability (ableism). While DEEPSYNC builds upon the visual identity established by the FETFX project, it also ventures beyond, forging a new image and personality that reflects its unique character and vision. Such visual identity takes inspiration from the following concepts:

- Innovation and deep tech
- A future for people that starts with people
- Empowering European innovators
- The three communities of practices: cleantech, digital/industry/space, and health innovation

Figure 1: EIC Communities logo

The logo for EIC Communities features a stylized blue icon on the left, resembling a square with a curved line inside, followed by the text "EIC COMMUNITIES" in a bold, blue, sans-serif font.

The official Brand book will be developed and shared among partners. It will serve as a rulebook for everyone involved in the project, particularly when developing communication and dissemination materials for specific events.

The brand book includes clear guidelines to allow partners to use it autonomously. Furthermore, it includes specifications regarding the use of the name, namely, when to use “EIC Communities” as the official project name, and when and how to refer to the platform DEEPSYNC.

Other information concerns the major branding elements: logo, colour palette and typography. All dissemination items and publications to be released by EIC Communities, including the project platform, will specify that the project has received funding from the European Union/European Innovation Council research and innovation programme and display the European emblem.

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3. The design process

The EIC Communities project launched its landing page in October 2023. It is available at this URL: www.deepsync.eu and www.eiccommunities.eu, with the first one being the primary domain. The DEEPSYNC platform domains were registered in Register.it. ICONS will manage hosting of the website until 4 years after the project ends. The full website will be available in March 2024.

The DEEPSYNC platform will be a living tool in continuous evolution as it will be regularly updated in terms of contents, new graphic layouts, tools, and features, in order to provide up-to-date information on both deep tech and the EIC beneficiaries' activities.

The website will use clear and simple terminology without the use of technical terms, aiming to be accessible to both experts and non-experts. The tone is designed to be "friendly and professional," intending to connect with both the professional audience and the wider public.

The objectives of the DEEPSYNC website are as follows:

- Offer resources and insights on the work of the European Innovation Council (EIC);
- Give visibility to the stories, innovations and results of the EIC beneficiaries, in order to engage multiple target audiences;
- Keep the audience of experts and non-experts updated on the news regarding the deep tech sector, the EIC events and projects;
- Build multidisciplinary and inclusive communities around selected projects by creating three thematic Communities of Practice (CoPs) - cleantech, health and digital/industry/space - that include also external stakeholders interested in their innovations.
- Encourage networking and exchanges between projects within and across the CoPs
- Stimulate people to follow and engage with the DEEPSYNC platform and its development

During the design process of the platform, ICONS identified all the possible user types that might interact with it, with the aim to customize graphic elements and the website functionalities to their needs. In the picture down below, it is possible to see the description of the four "personas" we identified as regular users. Personas are fictional characters or representations of our ideal platform users or target audience segments.

Figure 2: DEEPYNC personas

The four distinct "personas" we identified span a broad age range. What unites them is a common passion for innovation, research, and the dynamic realm of technology. Although not all of them are experts in these fields, they are all still interested in staying as up-to-date as possible on the latest news and discoveries.

For instance, while Francesco is the CEO of a start-up and a EIC beneficiary, Blanche works within the non-profit sector and lacks any training in science or technology.

All of these individuals use social media as a dynamic platform for sharing content that they find intriguing and noteworthy, posting about the latest news and stories. Caetano, whose job involves identifying trends and emerging technologies to acquire ahead of competitors, has a constant need to stay updated by reading scientific articles. On the other hand, Daria primarily conducts her research using official and institutional sources, specifically EU websites.

These personas were validated with EIC PMs during the co-creation workshop in Brussels. On that occasion, the ICONS team conducted a Mentimeter exercise involving questions directed at PMs about the importance and usefulness of various platform functions for the different user profiles explained above.

No additional personas were identified at this stage.

4. Landing page

The landing page was launched in October 2023 (M2) as an online reference to the project. It summarized the idea behind the project and its rationale, illustrating also its main goals and objectives. The layout was built on the project's visual identity.

Figure 3: DEEPSYNC landing page

At the end of the landing page is it also possible to find the project's social media contacts and the press release, published right after the kick off meeting in Rome in September 2023.

Figure 4: Social media links

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5. Website

The website will be designed to be simple and easy-to-navigate by anyone. It will also incorporate the database of WP1, which collects all the information about the project's stakeholders and their ecosystem. While the full website will be available in March 2024, the database will be integrated into the platform in April 2024.

The following table describes the main website sections which will be further developed by ICONS. This is not the final structure.

Table 1: Website sections

Section	Description
Homepage	This is the landing page of the DEEPSYNC website. It contains the title of the project, a short description, links to the social media channels and the pay off.
Stories	This section showcases the EIC beneficiaries' achievements and success stories through the format of news articles.
Events	It provides a compilation of all the events either hosted or endorsed by the project.
Database of EIC projects	It provides a collection of all the EIC projects involved in EIC Communities, organized in a way that makes it easy to access for the EIC beneficiaries and other interested users.
Database of Stakeholders	This section offers a list of stakeholders (companies and individuals) identified as paramount for the different EIC beneficiaries involved in the three CoPs.
EIC news	Sourced directly from the EIC website, it features news specifically tailored for the CoPs.
Audiovisual	It offers a diverse range of multimedia content, including brief videos, podcasts and interviews.
Privacy Notice	This section informs visitors about how their personal information is collected, used, and protected by the website or its operators.

6. Dissemination and monitoring

ICONS intends to promote the website through a comprehensive strategy that involves sharing it across DEEPSYNC's various social media platforms and leveraging a network of influential news amplifiers. This network consists of thematic media and specialized websites that are influential in spreading information about the deep tech sector within the European Union's news scene. These places are like fundamental in helping journalists, media experts, researchers, and the general public by making it easier for both scientific and regular news to travel all around the EU.

Project partners are also expected to contribute to the website dissemination via their own channels and stakeholder groups.

Over the course of the project ICONS will regularly monitor the DEEPSYNC website, to keep track of its performance. The necessary activity for this activity will be gathered with Matomo. Examples of relevant KPIs are number of website visits, flyer downloads, average time spent on pages and average session duration. Other interesting pieces of information are the most visited pages, the paths followed by users when navigating the website, the device used to access the website (computer, mobile phone or tablet), etc.

Reports on Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) activities (and hence on the website performance as well) will be included in D3.2 Updated Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities (February 2025). ICONS will use the collected monitoring data to evaluate possible corrective actions to maximise the impacts on society through the project DEC activities.

Access to DEEPSYNC outputs will be ensured beyond the lifetime of the project with an openly accessible repository for at least four years after the end of the project.

Conclusions

In the next few months ICONS will be responsible for developing and launching the website, which will be officially online in March 2024. In the meantime, ICONS already started the monitoring process of the landing page to regularly observe and assess its performance and effectiveness.

The ICONS team will continue its work on the visual identity, paying special attention to inclusive and accessible design.

The project website and its functionalities will be thoroughly described in D3.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities, available in February 2024. The first monitoring results will be presented to consortium partners during the next general assembly and reported in the D3.2 Updated Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities, available in February 2025.